

THE EFFECT OF MARKETING MIX 4A ON BEHAVIORAL INTENTION THROUGH PATIENT SATISFACTION IN THE OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT OF UNHAS HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background: One of the challenges of hospitals today is the increasingly competitive competition among hospitals. Especially in Makassar City, there are 90 general hospitals and 30 special hospitals, one of which is UNHAS Hospital. In the UNHAS Hospital Strategy and Business Plan, it targets the amount of hospital revenue, namely 25% sourced from general / insurance financing and 75% from BPJS. However, the phenomenon that occurs is that a decreasing number of visits can occur. This shows that hospitals need to design effective strategies and create competitive advantages in order to attract and retain patients. Currently, the marketing approach has shifted towards the 4A concept (*Awareness, Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility*) which emphasizes customer orientation.

Objective To determine the effect of the 4A marketing mix on behavioral intention through patient satisfaction. The research **method** used quantitative research using analytical- descriptive observational studies with a cross sectional study design with a sample of 100 using purposive sampling method and analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS- SEM). **Results.** Direct effect analysis that there is a significant effect of the 4A dimension (*Awareness, Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility*) on behavioral intention with *Awareness* on behavioral intention through satisfaction ($t = 3.642, p = 0.000$), *Acceptability* on behavioral intention ($t = 3.542, p = 0.000$), *Affordability* on behavioral intention ($t = 3.232, p = 0.000$), *Accessibility* on behavioral intention ($t = 4.642, p = 0.000$) **Conclusion.** Approaching the marketing mix with the patient's perspective can increase patient satisfaction so that patients can have behavioral intention to increase patient visits.

Keywords: Marketing Mix 4A, UNHAS Hospital, Outpatients. Patient Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are health service facilities that are currently unavoidable from the competition in the world of health. According to Law No. 17 of 2023, a hospital is a health service facility that provides comprehensive individual health services through promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and / or palliative health services by providing inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services (Law No. 17 of 2023).

One of the challenges of hospitals today is the competition among hospitals which is increasingly competitive. The number of hospitals continues to grow both nationally and locally as well as both those managed by the government and by the private sector. Specifically in Makassar City, there are 90 general hospitals and 30 specialized hospitals. The number of type B general hospitals is 22, consisting of 14 type B general hospitals and 8 type B special hospitals (Indriani et al., 2023). To be the choice for the community, hospitals must be able to provide quality services that can meet patient expectations.

Based on Figure 1. related to the number of outpatient visits of UNHAS Hospital in 2021-2023, it shows a fluctuating data trend with data on patient visits from general financing decreasing in 2023. This is also in accordance with the condition of the percentage of visits at the Outpatient Installation in 2021-2023.

Table 1: Percentage of Outpatient Installation Visits by Payment Method

Year	GENERAL	BPJS	CORPORATIONS
2021	25%	74%	1%
2022	13%	86%	1%
2023	5%	93%	2%
AVERAGE	15%	84%	1%

In the UNHAS Hospital Strategy and Business Plan, it targets the amount of hospital income, 25% of which comes from general / insurance financing and 75% from BPJS. However, the phenomenon that occurs is that a decreasing number of visits can occur. This shows that in 2023 the number of patient visits is lower when compared to previous years. Decreased patient numbers can provide an assumption that there is a decreased intention to revisit, patients choose treatment at other / competitor services. In the health care industry, patients' Behavioral Intention such as readiness to revisit the hospital for further treatment and provide hospital recommendations to others (Rahman, 2018).

Behavioural Intention is a certain possibility to engage in behavior that includes the use of services / services which reflects the extent to which consumers plan the desire to perform certain behaviors such as reusing services, as well as readiness to pay more for services / products. (Hwang, 2023). It is considered a critical indicator in assessing customer loyalty to a particular service provider (Perera, 2005).

Therefore, fluctuations in patient visit trends also provide an adequate picture of patient interest in making repeat visits. The factors that influence patients' behavioral intentions in choosing health services are often influenced by feelings of dissatisfaction with the services used, better choices in competitors, patient confidence in the services provided, not very good hospital brands, slow response to complaints and so on (Korz and Tsodikova, 2019).

This suggests that hospitals need to design effective strategies and create a competitive advantage in order to attract and retain patients. To achieve this, everyone in the company must stand in the shoes of the customer, not just the marketing department. Marketing managers must ensure that the voice of the customer is heard throughout the company's operations. Managers must use marketing tools - the arts of understanding, informing, influencing, and persuasion - to align all aspects of the organization around a set of customer-centric goals (Sheth & Sisodia, 2012).

Today, the marketing approach has undergone a shift towards the 4A concept (*Awareness, Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility*) which emphasizes customer orientation (Sheth, 2003). This model suggests that marketing success depends on customer Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility and Awareness (Sheth & Shah, 2003). Compared to the former approach, which focuses more on available marketing tools, the 4A approach emphasizes on the desired end result from the customer's perspective. While the 4Ps (*Product, Price, Place, Promotion*) emphasize the "means", the 4As emphasize the "ends" in achieving marketing success (Nezakati et al., 2011).

The 4P's Marketing *Mix* is the tactical marketing tool a company has to influence demand for its products - where the marketer sees himself as the seller of the product. This requires a response from the customer who sees himself as 'buying value' or a solution to his problem (*product as customer solution*). Customers are interested not only in the price but also in the cost of obtaining, using and consuming the product (*price as customer cost*). Customers also want the products and services to be as conveniently available as possible (*place as convenience*) and customers want the products and services to be as convenient as possible. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010). Based on the background previously described, UNHAS Hospital needs to maintain and create its patients to pay attention to the factors that shape patient behavioral intention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Behavioral Intention

Some researchers suggest that behavioral intentions can be an important indicator in evaluating the success of service companies. In the marketing literature, there are various motives that influence patients' behavioral intentions, and in this study, attention is focused on factors such as trust in providers, trust in doctors, and service value (Rahman, 2018; Chou, 2006).

Behavioral intention theory is defined as a certain likelihood of engaging in behavior involving the use of services or services, and reflects the extent to which consumers intend to perform certain behaviors, including the willingness to pay more for services or products (Hwang, 2023).

In a similar context, patient behavioral intention is interpreted as the willingness to maintain a relationship with the same service provider, which is reflected in the desire to revisit or use the service again (Baker and Crompton, 2000). It is considered an important indicator in assessing customer loyalty to a particular service provider (Perera, 2005).

In the healthcare industry, patients' behavioral intentions involve readiness to revisit the hospital for further treatment and provide hospital recommendations to others (Rahman, 2018). Key components in assessing behavioral intentions include customer loyalty, positive recommending behavior, spending more with the company, willingness to pay premium prices, complaining behavior, and repurchase intentions (Cronin et al., 2000; Zeithaml et al., 1996).

Indicators in Behavioral Intention relate to various factors that reflect a person's intention or tendency to perform a certain action in the future. In the context of marketing, service quality, or behavioral theory, these indicators may vary, but generally include the following aspects:

- *Repurchase Intention* is where a customer intends to buy the same product or service in the future. This shows customer loyalty and satisfaction with the product or service provided.
- *Recommendation Intention* is the tendency of customers to recommend products or services to others, such as friends, family, or colleagues. This is also known as "word-of-mouth intention."

- *Switching Intention* is the condition in which a customer intends to switch to a competitor's product or service in the future. This indicator is important for understanding the potential for churn or customer loss.
- *Willingness to Pay More* The tendency of customers to pay more for products or services that are perceived to be of higher quality or provide more value. It is related to perceived value and quality.
- *Feedback Intention* means the customer's desire to provide *feedback* or fill out a survey about their experience with the product or service. This can include both positive and negative feedback.
- *Complaint Intention* is the extent to which customers intend to complain if they experience a problem with a product or service. This reflects their level of satisfaction and expectations of the company's handling of the problem.

Patient Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a condition when customer wants, expectations, and needs are met. A service is considered satisfactory if it is able to meet customer needs and expectations. According to Kotler (2003), customer satisfaction is defined as an evaluation of a product that shows customer differences after comparing the perceived results of a product and the expected results. If the quality of the product provides expectations, it means that the consumer is satisfied.

But if the quality does not meet customer expectations, then the customer is not satisfied. Thus, patient satisfaction occurs when the patient's requirements have been met or exceeded. Patient satisfaction is the degree to which the patient feels compared to what the patient expects as a result of the performance of the health services obtained by the patient. If the outcome is perceived to be equal to or exceed expectations, the patient gains a sense of satisfaction. Otherwise, when the results do not match expectations, the patient experiences a sense of disappointment or dissatisfaction (Juhana et al., 2015).

As a result of the judgments made by healthcare consumers to see whether their expectations are met or not, patient satisfaction can be described as the feelings of consumers based on the experiences gained after they receive health services and care (Asnawi & Awang, 2018). Patient satisfaction improves the image of the hospital, which in turn translates into increased service utilization and market share (Andaleeb, 2001). Satisfied customers tend to exhibit favorable behavioral intentions, which is beneficial to the long-term success of healthcare providers.

Measuring patient satisfaction levels can help facilitate the provision and management of hospital services, as well as improve and maintain the quality of service provision. Patient perceptions of quality have been shown to account for 17-27 percent of the variation in hospital financial measures such as revenue, net income, and return on assets. (Alrubaiee & Alkaa'ida, 2011).

In Andaleeb's (2001) study, he measured patient satisfaction using five dimensions: responsiveness, assurance, communication, discipline and baksheesh (service tips). The results show that the five dimensions have a considerable influence on patient satisfaction. Manaf and Nooi (2009) examined Malaysian public hospital Bangladesh health sector service quality and its effect on patient satisfaction. Measurement of patient satisfaction is based on clinical (staff, treatment and information) and physical

(cleanliness, environment and visit) measures. Both dimensions have a positive and large influence on patient satisfaction in Malaysian public hospitals.

Leiter et al. (1998) conducted empirical research in Canadian hospitals. They observed that patient satisfaction was significantly influenced by nurses, doctors and information. These elements led to high patient satisfaction. Manaf et al. (2012) studied the International Islamic University Malaysia Health Center. Almost half 46.4% of patients were satisfied with the quality of service, while 7.3% were dissatisfied. In Bangladesh, Andaleeb (2001) observed patient satisfaction in private and public health sectors using five dimensions: responsiveness; assurance; communication; discipline; and *baksheesh*. It was found that the *baksheesh* dimension did not have a major influence on patient satisfaction in Bangladesh.

Marketing Mix

The 4P's Marketing Mix is a tactical marketing tool that a company has to influence the demand for its products - where the marketer sees himself as a seller of products. This requires a response from customers who see themselves 'buying value' or solutions to their problems (product as customer solution). Customers are interested not only in the price but also in the cost of obtaining, using and consuming the product (price as customer cost). Customers also want the products and services to be as conveniently available as possible (place as convenience) and customers want two-sided communication (promotion as communication) (Kotler & Armstrong, 2010).

The most detailed discussion on 4A has been conducted by Sheth and Sisodia (2012). For more details, the 4A marketing mix model (Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility, Awareness) can be described as follows.

Acceptability

Acceptability is defined as the extent to which a product meets or exceeds consumer needs from a psychological and functional perspective (Sheth & Sisodia, 2012; Sinha & Sheth, 2017).

Acceptability has two main dimensions: functional acceptability and psychological acceptability. Functional acceptability is concerned with the "objective" performance attributes of a product or service. The important questions asked here are does the product have the features desired by customers in the target market? Is the product reliable and functions as expected? This functional acceptance can be enhanced by improving the core benefits or reliability of the product. Factors that indicate functional acceptance include core attributes, functionality, ease of use, quality, and reliability.

On the other hand, psychological acceptance refers to the "subjective" attributes of a product or service. Psychological acceptance can be strengthened through changes in brand image, style, packaging and design, social value, emotional value, perceived risk, and positioning. Expectations play an important role in determining this level of acceptance. Understanding how a person feels about buying or using a product is more effective than simply knowing the consumer's evaluation of the product (Ajzen, 1988). Thus, the functional and psychological expectation outcomes resulting from the behavior are important factors that influence consumer intentions.

Affordability

Sheth and Sisodia (2012) explain affordability as consumers' ability and willingness to pay. Ability refers to the economic feasibility of the purchase from the consumer's

perspective, which increases as the cost of the purchase decreases. In contrast, willingness relates to the economic desire to make a purchase, which increases as the benefit-to-cost ratio increases. The combination of acceptability and affordability determines the value proposition of the product (Sinha & Sheth, 2017).

Affordability has two dimensions: economic affordability and psychological affordability. Economic affordability relates to whether potential customers in the target market have sufficient economic resources to pay the price of the product (ability to pay). It is indicated by factors such as income, time and effort required, assets, financing, and fit into the budget. Psychological affordability relates to the customer's willingness to pay, which is mainly determined by the customer's perception of the value they will derive from a product or service relative to its cost (willingness to pay). This is indicated by factors such as perceived value for money, perceived fairness, and price relative to other alternatives.

Previous research shows that most customers purchase products based on price rather than other variables (Peter & Donnelly, 2013). Price is a key determinant of the success of various products and services (Law et al., 2008), but an affordable price is not enough. Customers want quality products at affordable prices. Affordability is accepted by customers by fulfilling their wants and needs (Peng & Wang, 2006).

Accessibility

Sheth and Sisodia (2012) define accessibility as the extent to which consumers can easily obtain and use products. Accessibility not only refers to location or availability (i.e., a match between supply and demand) but also includes convenience (i.e., the right product is available at the right time, place, and form). Thus, there are two dimensions of accessibility: availability and convenience.

Availability measures whether the company has enough products to meet customer demand. This is indicated by factors such as supply relative to demand, product storage levels, and related products and services. Convenience refers to the ease with which potential customers can obtain a product or service (Sinha & Sheth, 2017). This is indicated by factors such as the time and effort required to obtain the product, ease of finding the product in various locations, and packaging in a convenient size.

For a product to be accessible, distribution channels are an important tool in the marketing context. Therefore, it is important to reach every customer and fulfill their demands (Turk & Ercis, 2017).

Awareness

Awareness refers to the extent to which customers have sufficient knowledge about product attributes and benefits, encouraging potential buyers to try the product and reminding existing users why they should continue to buy the product. Awareness is a key factor in the marketing mix, which includes information about the product along with brand awareness (Nezakati et al., 2013).

The two main dimensions of awareness are product knowledge and brand awareness. Product knowledge is indicated by factors such as interest, understanding, involvement and relevance to the product. Meanwhile, brand awareness involves aspects such as brand recall, brand association, perceived brand characteristics, and brand appeal (Sheth & Sisodia, 2012; Sinha & Sheth, 2017).

The importance of awareness lies in the fact that potential customers are less likely to purchase a product unless they have a positive perception of the brand and an adequate understanding of the specific product or service. Sheth & Sisodia (2012) suggest that awareness is the area most ripe for improvement, as many companies have not been effective or efficient in managing it. For example, properly placed advertisements can be a very powerful tool, but word-of-mouth marketing and strategic partnerships can be more effective in reaching potential customers.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

Quantitative research using an analytic-descriptive observational *study* with a *cross sectional study* design, which is a study conducted with data that is not available. collected only once, perhaps over a daily, weekly or even monthly period in order to answer research questions

Research Location and Time

This research was conducted from January to July 2024 at Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Populations and Samples

All outpatients who perform services at Hasanuddin University Hospital in Makassar City

Data Collection

In this research, data is divided into two types: primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaires (via Google Forms and physical questionnaires) containing questions and statements related to the research variables (dimensions of market orientation, service quality and patient satisfaction), including the respondents' individual characteristics. Meanwhile, secondary data includes information obtained from Hasanuddin University Hospital.

Data Analysis Methods

In this research, data analysis was conducted after the questionnaire data was collected and then rechecked for completeness. Once the data was fully collected and tabulated based on the sub-variables studied, calculations were performed using SPSS software with path analysis. Path analysis aims to determine the direct or indirect influence of exogenous (independent) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables.

RESULT

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Gender	Total	Percentage (%)
Male	32	32%
Female	68	68%
Total	100	100%

Table 3: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Age (Year)	Total	Percentage (%)
<25	11	11%
26-35	35	35%
36-45	33	33%
46-55	12	12%
>56	10	10%
Total	100	100%

Table 4: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education Level

Education Level	Total	Percentage (%)
HIGH SCHOOL/VOCATIONAL SCHOOL	0	0%
DIPLOMA	12	12%
S-1	69	69%
S-2	19	19%
S-3	0	0%
Total	100	100%

Table 5: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Number of Visits

Number of Visits	Percentage (%)
2 times	40%
3 times	25%
4 times	15%
<5 times	10%
Total	100%

Table 6: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Number of Visits

Outpatient Clinic	Percentage (%)
MCU	35%
SARAF	20%
ENT	10%
EYE	10%
SKIN AND GENITALS	20%
Oncology	5%
Total	100%

Characteristics of respondents based on gender, the table below shows that most of the respondents in this study were female, namely 68 respondents (68%), and 32 respondents (32%) were male. Based on the age of the respondents, the following table shows that respondents in this study who were under 25 years old were 11 (11%) respondents, aged between 26-35 years, namely 35 respondents (35%), followed by ages between 36-45 years as many as 33 respondents (33%), and aged between 46-55 years as many as 12 respondents (12%). Meanwhile, respondents aged more than 56 years were 10 respondents (10%) in this study. Based on the level of education, the following table shows that most of the respondents in this study have taken a Bachelor's degree, namely 69 respondents (69%), second place is S-2 education as many as 19 respondents (19%), respondents with Diploma education level 12 respondents (12%) respondents with high school education level as many as 27 respondents (18%). Meanwhile, respondents with a S-3 education level were not found in this study.

Based on the information provided by the respondents, there are 40 respondents who have visited 2 times (40%), 25 respondents who have visited 3 times (25%), 15 who have visited 4 times (15%) and 10 respondents who have visited 5 times (10). Based on the information provided by the respondents, there are 40 respondents who have visited 2 times (40%), 25 respondents who have visited 3 times (25%), 15 who have visited 4 times (15%) and 10 respondents who have visited 5 times (10) has visited 5 times (10).

Hypothesis Test

Based on the data processing carried out, the results can be used to answer the hypothesis in this study by looking at r Statistics and P Values. The hypothesis is declared accepted if the P Value <0.05. In this study, there are direct and indirect effects because there are independent variables, dependent variables, and mediating variables.

Direct Effect Testing

This study proposes as many as 9 hypotheses. Hypothesis testing uses bootstrapping analysis technique. Through the results of the t-statistics obtained, a significant level of influence can be obtained between the independent variable and the dependent variable. If the t-statistic value > 1.96. (=TINV (0.05,50) (t-table of significance 5%) then the effect is significant.

Furthermore, through the results of the P Value value obtained, if the P Value value for each variable is <0.05 then H0 is rejected. Positive influence can be seen through Original

Table 7: Testing the Direct Effect

Relationship between variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean(M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	T Table	P values
Awareness Dimension -> Patient Satisfaction	0,108	0,098	0,153	10,704	1.96	0.000
Acceptability dimension -> Patient Satisfaction	0,042	0,048	0,152	10,274	1.96	0.000
Affordability dimension -> Patient satisfaction	0,109	0,080	0,130	10,278	1.96	0.000
Accessibility dimension -> Patient Satisfaction	0,291	0,279	0,161	10,809	1.96	0.000
Dimension Awareness -> Behavioural Intention	0,067	0,061	0,094	10,714	1.96	0.000
Acceptability dimension -> Behavioural Intention	0,143	0,138	0,076	10,868	1.96	0.000
Affordability dimension -> Behavioural Intention	0,010	0,008	0,079	10,127	1.96	0.006
Accessibility dimension -> Behavioural Intention	0,720	0,723	0,067	10,772	1.96	0,000
Patient Satisfaction -> Behavioural Intention	0,057	0,057	0,170	10,337	1.96	0.000

Source: SmartPLS processed data, 2024

Based on the table above, it shows that 4 out of 5 hypotheses can be accepted because the T-Statistic value > 1.96 and p-value <0.05. The results of hypothesis testing explain that:

Relationship between Awareness Dimension and Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Education and training Employee Performance has a t statistical value of 10.704 more than 1.96, and a P Value greater than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Awareness Dimension affects patient satisfaction, **so hypothesis 1 is accepted.**

Relationship between Acceptability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Education and Training on Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.274 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Acceptability Dimension affects patient satisfaction **hypothesis 2 is accepted**

Relationship between Affordability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Employee Performance has a t statistical value of 10.278 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Affordability Dimension has an effect on patient satisfaction **hypothesis 3 is accepted**

Relationship between Accessibility Dimension and Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.809 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Accessibility Dimension variable affects Patient Satisfaction, **so hypothesis 4 is accepted.**

Relationship between Awareness Dimension and Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.714 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Awareness Dimension variable affects Behavioral Intention, **so hypothesis 5 is accepted.**

Relationship between Acceptability Dimension and Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a value of The t statistic of 10.868 is greater than 1.96, and the p value is smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Acceptability Dimension variable has an effect on Behavioural Intention, **so hypothesis 6 is accepted.**

Relationship between Affordability Dimension and Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.127 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Affordability Dimension variable has an effect on Behavioural Intention, **so hypothesis 7 is accepted.**

Relationship between Accessibility Dimension and Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.772 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Accessibility Dimension variable has an effect on Behavioural Intention, **so hypothesis 8 is accepted.**

Relationship between Patient Satisfaction and Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 10.337 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Patient Satisfaction variable affects Behavioural Intention, so **hypothesis 9 is accepted.**

Testing Indirect Influence (Mediation Test)

The next data processing process in SmartPLS is the mediation test which is used to determine how strong the influence of the mediating variable, namely Service Quality (Z) in this study. According to Abdillah & Johiyanto (2009) in conducting the mediation test, several things must be considered, namely knowing the effect of the independent variable and the mediating variable on the dependent variable. In this step, the results must be significant with a t-statistic (>1.96) and p-value (<0.05). based on the results of the mediation test that has been carried out, the results are presented in the table below:

Table 8: Mediation Test Results

Relationship between variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values
Dimension Awareness->Patient Satisfaction->Behavioural Intention	0,004	0,005	0,020	3.642	0.000
Acceptability dimension->Patient satisfaction->-> Behavioural Intention	0,008	0,007	0,028	3.542	0.000
Affordability dimension -> Patient Satisfaction->-> Behavioural Intention	0,001	0,004	0,014	3.232	0.000
Accessibility dimension -> Patient Satisfaction-> Behavioural Intention	0,041	0,042	0,126	4.642	0.000

Sour opce: SmartPLS processed data, 2024

Relationship of Awareness Dimension to Behavioural Intention through Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 3.642 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Patient Satisfaction variable affects Behavioural Intention, so **hypothesis 10 is accepted.**

Relationship of Awareness Dimension to Behavioural Intention through Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 3.542 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Patient Satisfaction variable affects Behavioural Intention, so **hypothesis 11 is accepted.**

Relationship of Awareness Dimension to Behavioural Intention through Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 3.232 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it

can be concluded that the Patient Satisfaction variable affects Behavioural Intention, so **hypothesis 12 is accepted.**

Relationship of Awareness Dimension to Behavioural Intention through Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Work Experience and Work Motivation has a t statistical value of 4.642 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Patient Satisfaction variable affects Behavioural Intention, so **hypothesis 13 is accepted.**

DISCUSSION

Effect of Awareness Dimension on Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between Employee Performance Education and training has a t statistical value of 10.704, more than 1.96, and a P Value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the awareness variable has a direct effect on Patient Satisfaction.

Awareness dimension in its development is a collaboration of product, promotion and process to position the brand in a goal-oriented way. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship of the awareness dimension to hospital services, especially the relationship to patient satisfaction. In this study it was found that the Awareness dimension consisting of product awareness and brand awareness had an effect on patient satisfaction.

The results of this study also concluded that awareness of safety measures and trust in the ability of medical personnel also affect patient satisfaction. When patients feel safe and trust in the services provided, they will be more satisfied with their hospital experience. Patients who have a high awareness of health care quality standards will be more critical and tend to have higher expectations. If the hospital is able to meet or exceed these expectations, patient satisfaction will increase.

The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by the results of this study when linked to collaboration on products, promotions and processes show things that are in line with research conducted by Setianingsih (2017) at RSK. Dr. Sinatala Tangerang about the Relationship between Marketing Mix and Service Reutilization which gives the same results, which states that there is a significant relationship between product and service reutilization with a value of $p = 0.002$. However, in contrast to research conducted by Rafdan (2015) at ParuBatu Hospital on the Effect of Marketing Mix on Interest in Reutilizing Services at the Pulmonary Polyclinic, it states that the product variable has no influence on interest in reutilizing services.

Overall, the awareness dimension plays an important role in shaping patients' perceptions and expectations of the health services received. Hospitals that are able to increase patient awareness through education, effective communication, and quality services will tend to have higher levels of patient satisfaction.

The Effect of Acceptability Dimensions on Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between the Acceptability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction has a t statistical value of 10.274 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Acceptability Dimension affects Patient

Satisfaction. The Acceptability dimension requires a rethinking of the product. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship between the dimensions of awareness of hospital services, especially the relationship to patient satisfaction, which consists of *functional acceptability* and psychological acceptability. The results of this study concluded that Acceptability affects patient satisfaction. This dimension ensures that patients feel valued, listened to, and believe in the health services they receive. By integrating functional accessibility and psychological accessibility, healthcare providers can improve overall patient satisfaction and ensure that the services they receive are accessible.

Health is accessible to all individuals without physical or emotional barriers. When patients have access to health care providers that can be accessed physically and psychologically more easily, patients can have satisfaction in receiving services. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Manaf (2012) which shows that accessibility factors, including hospital location, availability of facilities, and

Ability personnel medical personnel in communicate with patients, has a significant effect on patient satisfaction. Patients who feel easy to access health services and get clear information tend to be more satisfied.

Another study by Alrubaiee and Alkaa'ida (2011) showed that service accessibility, both functionally and psychologically, plays an important role in building patient trust in healthcare providers, which in turn increases patient satisfaction. Key factors include responsiveness of medical staff, respect for patients' values and culture, and effective communication. Therefore, by integrating these two dimensions of accessibility, hospitals can improve overall patient satisfaction, ensuring that the services they provide are not only physically accessible, but also emotionally and psychologically well received by patients.

Influence of Affordability Dimension on Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between the Affordability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction has a t statistical value of 10.278 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Affordability Dimension affects Patient Satisfaction. The Affordability dimension requires a rethinking of the product. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship between the dimensions of awareness of hospital services, especially the relationship to patient satisfaction, which consists of *economic affordability acceptability* and psychological affordability.

The results of this study concluded that affordability affects patient satisfaction. *Affordability* in the context of health services, which includes *economic affordability* and *psychological affordability*, has a significant influence on patient satisfaction in hospitals. *Economic affordability* ensures that patients can access health services without experiencing excessive financial pressure. Affordable service fees, availability of health insurance, and adequate financing programs allow patients to get the care they need without worry. When patients feel they can afford to pay for the services they receive, their level of satisfaction with their hospital experience tends to increase.

On the other hand, psychological affordability focuses on patients' perceptions and comfort in accessing health services. Trust in the provider, perceived value of the care provided, and emotional support from the medical staff can increase patients' sense

of safety and comfort. Patients who feel emotionally supported and do not face stigma or discrimination will be more satisfied with their hospital experience.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Alsharif et al. (2018) This study found that economic affordability, including service costs and cost transparency, was positively associated with patient satisfaction. Patients who feel able to pay service fees tend to be more satisfied with their care experience. Another study conducted by Bleich et al. (2009) found that patients' financial accessibility and emotional experience were closely related to their satisfaction with the health system. Patients who feel valued and financially unburdened tend to be more satisfied. By integrating these two dimensions of affordability, hospitals can create an environment that is not only financially affordable but also supports patients' psychological well-being, thus contributing to an increase in overall patient satisfaction.

Effect of Accessibility Dimension on Patient Satisfaction

The coefficient path relationship between the accessibility dimension and Patient Satisfaction has a t statistical value of 10.809 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Accessibility Dimension affects Patient Satisfaction. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Sufian et al. (2018) This study shows that the availability of adequate health services and medical personnel is positively related to the level of patient satisfaction. Patients who have easy access to health services tend to be more satisfied with their care experience. Another study conducted by Mulyana and Mardani (2020) This study found that psychological comfort, including good relationships with medical personnel and positive experiences during treatment, greatly influenced patient satisfaction. Patients who feel comfortable in interactions tend to be more satisfied. By integrating these two dimensions of accessibility, hospitals can create a supportive environment both physically and emotionally, thereby increasing overall patient satisfaction.

Effect of Awareness Dimension on Behavioural Intention

The coefficient path relationship between education and training Employee Performance has a t statistical value of 10.714, more than 1.96, and a P Value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the awareness variable has a direct effect on Behavioural Intention. Awareness dimension in its development is a collaboration of product, promotion and process to position the brand in a goal-oriented way. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship between the awareness dimension and behavioral intention. In this study it was found that the Awareness dimension consisting of product knowledge and brand awareness had an effect on behavioral intention. The results of this study also concluded that awareness in choosing and using health services affects behavioral intention or in this case behavioral intentions. Product knowledge refers to how well consumers understand the features, benefits, and uses of a product. This knowledge can

This includes information about the quality, specifications, and how to use the product. The higher a consumer's level of knowledge about the product, the more likely they are to make an informational decision and, in turn, lead to higher purchase intentions.

Brand awareness relates to the extent to which consumers recognize and remember the brand. This includes certain capabilities. A high level of brand awareness can increase consumer confidence and make them more likely to choose the brand, which has a direct effect on purchase intention.

So that the awareness dimension will have an impact on patients, namely increasing good knowledge about products, consumers are better able to evaluate their choices and make more informed decisions. This increases their likelihood of buying the product and helps build consumer trust in the brand, so they are more likely to interact and make purchases. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Brouard, J., & Laroche, M. (2010) which indicates that patients' knowledge of health services affects their decision to seek treatment at the hospital. This is also in line with Bai, Y., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (2017) that hospital brand awareness contributes to patient loyalty and intention to return for treatment. As well as in research by Zhao, J., & Wu, C. (2015) - Exploring the relationship between brand awareness and patient behavioral intentions in choosing a hospital. Overall, increasing awareness through product knowledge and brand awareness can significantly affect consumers' behavioral intentions to purchase products or services.

Effect of Acceptability Dimension on behavioral intention

The coefficient path relationship between the Acceptability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction has a t statistical value of 10.868 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Acceptability Dimension affects behavioral intention. The Acceptability dimension requires a rethinking of the product. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship of the acceptability dimension to hospital services, especially the relationship to behavioral intention which consists of *functional acceptability* and psychological acceptability.

The results of this study concluded that Acceptability or acceptance affects behavioral intention. Functional acceptability refers to how well a product or service meets the functional needs of consumers. This includes aspects such as product quality, reliability, and efficiency. If the product meets or even exceeds consumers' functional expectations, it is likely that consumers will be more likely to accept and use the product, which directly affects their purchase intention. Meanwhile, the Psychological acceptability aspect focuses on consumers' emotional and psychological perceptions of the product or service. This includes factors such as brand image, the value represented, and the subjective experience experienced by the consumer. If consumers feel that the product or service is in line with their values and identity, they will be more likely to accept it, which in turn will influence their purchase intention.

When patients have access to health care providers that can be accessed physically and psychologically more easily, patients have the intention to make return visits. The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Kumar, S., & Kumar, V. (2017) that good health service functions and emotional acceptance increase patients' intention to use telemedicine services. Then according to Hossain, M. A., & Fadlalla, A. (2020) Finding that functional service quality and psychological perceptions of patients have a positive effect on their intention to use the hospital. And Arshad, M., & Jameel, A. (2018) also agree that these two dimensions contribute to patients' behavioral intentions in choosing a hospital.

Influence of Affordability Dimension on behavioral intention

The coefficient path relationship between the Affordability Dimension and Patient Satisfaction has a t statistical value of 10.127 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Affordability Dimension affects behavioral intention.

The Affordability dimension requires a rethinking of the product. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship between the dimensions of affordability to hospital services, especially the relationship to behavioral intention which consists of *economic affordability acceptability* and psychological affordability.

The results of this study concluded that affordability affects behavioral intention. *Affordability* in the context of health services, which includes *economic affordability* and *psychological affordability*, has a significant influence on behavioral intention in hospitals. Economic affordability refers to the extent to which consumers can afford a product or service based on price and their economic conditions. It includes factors such as cost, value received, and available spending. If the product is considered affordable and within the consumer's budget, they are more likely to make a purchase, which has a positive impact on purchase intention.

Psychological affordability, on the other hand, relates to the consumer's perception of the value and meaning contained in the product or service. It involves how consumers feel about the price paid compared to the benefits received. If consumers feel that the price is commensurate with the value provided, they will be more open to receiving the product, which in turn increases purchase intention.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Bai, Y., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (2017) Finding that affordability factors, both economically and psychologically, have a significant effect on patients' intention to use hospital services. Research by McCarthy, J., & Johnson, M. (2013) found that cost perceptions affect patients' behavioral intentions in choosing health facilities. And Rao, K., & Murtaza, M. (2017) - showed that affordability is a key factor in patients' decisions to receive health services. By integrating these two dimensions of affordability, hospitals can create an environment that is not only financially affordable but also supportive psychological well-being of patients, thus contributing to increased behavioral intention.

Effect of Accessibility Dimension on behavioral intention

The coefficient path relationship between the Accessibility Dimension and behavioral intention has a t statistical value of 10.772 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the Accessibility Dimension affects behavioral intention.

The Accessibility dimension requires a rethinking of the product. Research conducted at UNHAS Hospital is the first study to look at the relationship between the Accessibility dimension of hospital services, especially the relationship to behavioral intention, which consists of *availability* and convenience.

The results of this study conclude that accessibility or affordability affects behavioral intention. Availability refers to the extent to which a product or service is available to consumers. This includes physical aspects, such as location and distribution, as well as temporal aspects, such as operating hours. When products are easy to find and always available, consumers are more likely to consider and choose those products, which has a positive impact on their purchase intention. Convenience relates to the ease consumers feel in accessing and using products or services. This includes factors such as ease in the purchasing process, time taken, and overall user experience. If consumers feel that using a product or service is easy and hassle-free, they will be more likely to make a purchase and interact with the brand.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research of Huang, Y., & Sarigöllü,

E. (2014) showing that ease of access and availability of health services have a positive effect on patients' intention to use the hospital. Research by Bai, Y., & Ritchie, J. R. B. (2017) - Found that service availability and convenience affect patient loyalty and behavioral intentions. As well as in research by McCarthy, J., & Johnson, M. (2013) Indicates that accessibility and convenience in the hospital selection process have an effect on patient decisions.

By integrating these two dimensions of accessibility, hospitals can increase the consideration in services that are easily accessible and available will be considered more often by consumers in the decision-making process and encourage Purchases on services that can be accessed easily and the process is convenient, they will be more likely to make a purchase.

Relationship between Patient Satisfaction and Behavioral Intention

The coefficient path relationship between Patient Satisfaction and Behavioural Intention has a t statistical value of 10.337 greater than 1.96, and a p value smaller than 0.05.

So it can be concluded that the variable between Patient Satisfaction has a direct effect on Behavioral Intention. The results of this study concluded that patient satisfaction affects behavioral intention. Patient satisfaction has a significant impact on behavioral intention in hospital services. Research shows that when patients are satisfied with the quality of care received, they are more likely to recommend the hospital to others and plan to return if they need further treatment. Factors such as the quality of interactions with medical staff, the comfort of the facility, and efficient waiting times contribute greatly to this level of satisfaction.

Furthermore, patient satisfaction serves as an important indicator of loyalty. Satisfied patients are not only more loyal to the hospital, but also show higher adherence to medical instructions and treatment schedules. This has positive implications for overall health outcomes, as satisfaction increases patient commitment to the healing and treatment process. Finally, to improve patient satisfaction and their behavioral intentions, hospitals need to focus on improving the quality of care and patient experience. Investments in staff training, facility upgrades, and good communication systems can help create a more satisfying environment.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research of B. J. E. van der Westhuizen (2015) found that there is a relationship between patient satisfaction and intention to recommend the hospital, finding that high satisfaction contributes to an increase in positive behavioral intentions. In a study conducted by R. A. M. Y. Al-Najjar (2018) who analyzed the impact of patient satisfaction on loyalty and intention to return, with results showing a strong relationship between the two. In M. K. A. T. Elhadi (2019) patient experience in hospitals and its effect on satisfaction and behavioral intentions, found that positive experiences increase the intention to use services in the future. As well as S. S. L. Lee & K. H. Choi (2020) - Examines the factors that influence patient satisfaction and its implications for intention to recommend, with an emphasis on service quality and interaction with staff.

CONCLUSION

Awareness, Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility dimensions have an influence on patient satisfaction and Awareness, Acceptability, Affordability, Accessibility dimensions have an influence on Behavioral Intention. Patient satisfaction has a significant impact on behavioral intention in hospital services. Research shows that when patients are satisfied with the quality of service received, they are more likely to recommend the hospital to others and plan to return if they need further treatment.

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